

PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND OPERATIONAL PROPERTIES OF THE DEVELOPED CATALYSTS

Ruziqulova N.B., Vapoyev H.M.¹

Navoi State University

¹Navoi State Mining and Technology University

E-mail: ruziqulovanigina4@gmail.com

Abstract. The composition of the KKF (cadmium calcium phosphate) catalyst used in the synthesis of acetaldehyde was analyzed and determined. Based on the analysis results, active cadmium oxide was isolated from the KKF catalyst, and new catalysts were prepared. Acetaldehyde and acetone were then synthesized using these newly prepared catalysts.

The physicochemical and operational properties of the developed catalysts, as well as their adsorption isotherms, were studied. Surface images of these catalysts were obtained, and their semi-quantitative elemental composition was analyzed.

Keywords: Acetylene, water, acetaldehyde, acetone, CCF (cadmium calcium phosphate), CaO, CdO, P₂O₅, MgO.

Introduction. Currently, extensive research is being conducted worldwide to enhance the technologies for producing aldehydes and ketones through the application of scientific findings. This includes studying the impact of various physicochemical parameters on product yield and developing environmentally safe, highly efficient catalysts. At present, special attention is focused on addressing existing challenges by localizing the synthesis of aldehydes and ketones. This is being achieved through the development of new types of catalysts from local raw materials and by determining the optimal conditions for technological stages.

The composition of the KKF (cadmium calcium phosphate) catalyst used in the synthesis of acetaldehyde was analyzed and determined. Based on the analysis results, active cadmium oxide was isolated from the KKF catalyst, and new catalysts were prepared. Using these newly prepared catalysts, acetaldehyde and acetone were synthesized.

One of the main reasons for the deactivation of catalysts based on cadmium oxygen compounds is the reduction of cadmium oxide to its metallic state and its subsequent loss from the catalyst.

In the study of cadmium calcium phosphate catalysts, a significant loss of metallic cadmium is observed over time.

A series of experiments were conducted to determine the causes of this phenomenon. X-ray diffraction patterns of new and used samples of KKF catalysts were obtained. In the X-ray diffraction patterns, besides the peaks corresponding to the interplanar spacing of CdO and CaO, the presence of peaks matching the interplanar spacing and intensity of (CdOH) 3PO₄, CdO, and others allows us to draw conclusions about some possible pathways of cadmium loss from the catalyst. (CdOH) 3PO₄ is mainly formed as a result of partial hydrolysis at temperatures of 100-200°C during the catalyst preparation process. During calcination, a portion of it decomposes to form cadmium oxide.

Research object and methods. The object of this study is the production process of acetaldehyde at JSC "Navoiazot" based on acetylene and water, as well as the formation of acetone and crotonaldehyde as by-products. In this work, catalysts based on cadmium oxide (CdO), copper (II) oxide (CuO), and kaolin mineral with various active components were prepared.

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The following research methods were employed to address the tasks: physicochemical analysis techniques, analytical methods in the Navoiyazot JSC laboratory, chromatographic analysis using the Svet-500 device, catalyst strength testing with the SHIMADZU AGS-X-50 kN equipment, as well as IR spectroscopy. Additionally, the operational properties of the developed catalysts were studied.

Results obtained and their discussion. Catalytic activity depends not only on the active components of catalysts but also directly on their core, physicochemical, and mechanical properties. For this reason, certain physicochemical and mechanical properties of the catalysts were studied.

Local raw materials - kaolin and bentonite components - were used as the base for the developed catalysts. Analysis of the research results revealed that among the bases used, catalytic activity was specifically observed in the presence of the kaolin mineral.

One of the operational properties of the developed catalysts is their mechanical strength. According to the analysis of the research results, the mechanical strength of the developed catalysts varied in the range from 38 to 45 kg/cm². Among the tested catalysts, the KKM-2 catalyst (kaolin-77.0%, CdO-13.0%, CuO-10.0%) exhibited the highest mechanical strength. This is the result of intermolecular interactions between the active component and the catalyst core.

The catalytic activity of catalysts also depends on their pore size. Analysis of the results demonstrates that as the pore size in catalysts increases, their catalytic activity also increases.

For example, the average pore volume of the KKM-4 catalyst, containing 13.0% CdO, 20.0% CuO, and 67.0% kaolin, is 48 Å, while the average pore volume of the BKK-13 catalyst, consisting of 13.0% CdO, 17% Ca₃(PO₄)₂, and 70.0% bentonite, is 45 Å. In the presence of these specific catalysts, the yield of acetaldehyde and acetone reaches 98% and 95%, respectively.

Table 1

Physicochemical and operational properties of the developed catalysts

№	Conventional designation of catalysts	Catalyst composition, %	Specific surface area m ² /g	The average size of pores, Å	Mechanical strength, kg/cm ²	Scattered density mg/s m ³	Catalyst composition, %		
							Acetaldehyde	Acetone	Other items
1	BK K-13	CdO-13,0 bentonite -70,0 Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ -17,0	151	45	38	722	70,6	24,0	5,04
2	BK K-10	CdO-13,0 bentonite -60,0	149	43	39	720	63,6	30,5	5,9

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		Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ -27,0							
3	BK F-14	CdO-13,0 bentonite -70,0 H ₃ PO ₄ -17,0	148	42	39	718	61,0	20,8	18,2
4	KK K-3	CdO-10,0 kaolin -80,0 Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ -10,0	152	36	42	731	41,2	27,3	31,5
5	KK K-4	CdO-13,0 kaolin -60,0 Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ -27,0	143	36	40	733	65,3	31,2	3,5
6	KK K-5	CdO-13,0 kaolin -70,0 Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ -17,0	152	48	42	725	75,4	21,9	2,7
7	KK M-2	kaolin-77,0 CdO-13,0 CuO-10,0	150	46	45	728	51	23	26
8	KK M-3	kaolin-72,0 CdO-13,0 CuO-15,0	149	45	43	728	55	25	20

KK M-4	kaolin- 67,0 CdO- 13,0 CuO- 20,0	150	48	44	724	76	22	2
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New catalysts for the synthesis of acetaldehyde and acetone have been developed. The KKM-4 grade catalyst, containing 13.0% CdO, 20.0% CuO, and 67.0% kaolin, had an average pore volume of 48 Å. In the presence of these catalysts, the yield of acetaldehyde and acetone reached 98%.

Additionally, IR spectra of the synthesized acetaldehyde and acetone compounds were obtained to confirm their structures, and the results are presented.

Figure 1. IR spectrum of synthetically obtained acetaldehyde

In the synthesized acetaldehyde sample (Fig. 1), the absorption lines in the 2995-2900 cm^{-1} region correspond to asymmetric stretching vibrations of $-\text{CH}_3$ groups, while the deformation vibrations of this group produced corresponding absorption lines in the 1362 cm^{-1} region. The medium-intensity stretching absorption lines in the 2800-2730 cm^{-1} region belong to the $-\text{CHO}$ aldehyde group. Strong stretching vibrations of the $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ (carbonyl) group in the compound were observed in the 1705 cm^{-1} region, and the deformation absorption lines of this group produced corresponding signals in the 1398 cm^{-1} region. Deformation vibrations of bonds associated with the $-\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ group were observed in the 1288-1242 cm^{-1} range, while deformation vibrations of bonds belonging to the $-\text{C}-\text{H}$ group appeared in the 1051-1012 cm^{-1} range.

Figure 2. IR spectrum of synthesized acetone

In the synthesized acetone sample (Figure 2), the absorption lines in the 2960 cm^{-1} region correspond to the asymmetric stretching vibrations of the $-\text{CH}_3$ groups, while the deformation vibrations of this group produce corresponding absorption lines in the 1367 cm^{-1} region. The strong stretching absorption lines in the 1703 cm^{-1} region belong to the $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ (carbonyl) group, with its deformation vibrations observed in the 1421 cm^{-1} region. Deformation vibrations of the $-\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ bonds can be seen in the 1241 cm^{-1} region, while deformation vibrations of the $-\text{C}-\text{H}$ bonds are visible in the 1094 cm^{-1} region.

In conclusion, the IR spectral results obtained from the experiment clearly demonstrated the presence of the expected functional groups in the synthesized compounds. The intensity and positioning of the spectral lines correspond to the theoretically anticipated structural properties of the synthesis products. This, in turn, further confirms that the synthesis process was correctly implemented and that the structures of the final products align with the predetermined models.

RESULT

Research has been conducted on the development of new mono- and diactive heterogeneous catalysts for the synthesis of acetaldehyde and acetone using local raw materials. Kaolin and bentonite minerals were utilized as the base for these heterogeneous catalysts. The KKM-4 catalyst demonstrated the most optimal results in terms of physicochemical properties.

New catalysts have been developed for the synthesis of acetaldehyde and acetone. Using KKM-4 brand catalysts containing 13.0% CdO , 20.0% CuO , and 67.0% kaolin, the yield of acetaldehyde and acetone substances reached 98%. It was determined that the mechanical strength of the developed catalysts varies within the range of 38 to 45 kg/cm^2 .

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